

Semiconducting Behavior of Eutectic Composites

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ABSTRACT

Bulk crystals of semiconducting SnSe-SnSe₂ eutectic composites have been successfully grown by the directional solidification technique with a temperature gradient of 110°C per cm and a growth rate of 0.5 cm per hr. The multi-p/n-junction characteristics of these eutectics were revealed by measuring their cleaved layers with a hot probe. From the reflectance data of the eutectic in the infrared region, it was tentatively concluded that the SnSe-SnSe₂ eutectic is a nondegenerate semiconductor. The current voltage data, obtained from a SnSe-SnSe₂ single p-n junction solar cell, indicated that multi-p/n junction eutectics are potential materials for solid-state device applications.

INTRODUCTION

Controlled eutectic composites for structural application have been extensively investigated. However, very little has been known for nonstructural applications. In recent years, some work on potential applications of controlled eutectic composites have been summarized and reviewed (1-5). In general, these applications are mainly based on the combination of electrical, magnetic, optical, and thermal properties. Although electronic devices, such as Magneto Resistors (6), Infrared Detectors (7), light sources (8), and Infrared Polarizers (6,9,10), have been reported, these devices are still at their infant stages for uses.

In semiconducting eutectic composites, efforts were paid to eutectic systems which consist of III-V semiconductor phases, such as GaAs, InSb, and GaSb, and metal fiber phases, (11-14). The interfaces of these metal semiconducting eutectic composites are similar to a series of Schottky diode junctions. It is conceivable that other types of semiconducting eutectics consisting of two semiconducting phases could play an important role in multi-p/n-junction device applications.

The objectives of this paper are (1) to grow the semiconducting SnSe-SnSe₂ eutectic composite from the liquid phase and (2) to investigate the semiconducting behavior of the SnSe-SnSe₂ eutectic composite in terms of infrared reflectivity and current-voltage characteristics. The experimental results will be presented with discussions.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Crystal Growth of SnSe-SnSe₂ Eutectics

Tin shots of 99.9999 purity (Cominco American, Inc., Spokane, Washington) and selenium shots of 99.999⁺ purity (ROC/RIC, Sun Valley, CA) were weighed at 50.9933 wt.% selenium and loaded in a previously cleaned fused-quartz tube with one conical end closed. All the sealed ampoules were vacuum-sealed at a pressure less than 10⁻⁶ Torr and homogenized at 800°C for 4 days and then slowly cooled. Homogenization at lower temperatures tends to produce voids in the ingots. These voids are believed to be remnants of the unreacted selenium. Homogenization of a SnSe-SnSe₂ eutectic charge prepared from the Sn and Se elements was conducted at a temperature higher than the melting point of the SnSe₂ (657°C). A longer time was needed for a complete homogenization.

The homogenized charge showed a shining and smooth surface which indicates no reaction between the melt and the quartz-tube wall. The homogenized ampoule was then placed inside a graphite crucible and covered with a graphite cap. A small amount of graphite powder was packed between the tip of the ampoule and the graphite crucible to provide an intimate contact. The graphite crucible minimizes the temperature fluctuation due to its thermal mass and allows a steep temperature profile through a water-cooled copper supporter underneath. The graphite crucible is protected from oxidation by inserting it in a large size quartz container under vacuum. This whole assembly is inserted in the three-zone furnace which is mounted on a frame of a Lepel crystal growth unit and can be moved up and down at a controlled speed.

The SnSe-SnSe₂ eutectic ingots were grown at a growth rate of approximately 0.5 cm/hr. and at an estimated temperature gradient of 110°C/cm. Figure 1 shows some of these grown ingots which tend to have hollow striations along the grain boundaries of the surface. It is believed that these striations are related to the curvature of the quartz tube.

Wafer Preparation

Great care has been taken during the handling of SnSe-SnSe₂ eutectic ingots because they are very fragile. A string saw (Laser Tech., Inc., No. Hollywood, CA) was used to slice the ingot into wafers of 150 mil thick, either parallel or perpendicular to the ingot axis. Figure 2 shows the thin SnSe-SnSe₂ eutectic wafers.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Microstructure of SnSe-SnSe₂ Eutectics

A variety of mixed acids have been used to preferentially etch out one of the two phases of the eutectics. It was found that a solution made of 1 HF and 1 HNO₃ can successfully etch away the SnSe phase in one minute leaving the unetched SnSe₂ phase protruding out of the surface. It is believed that the etching process involves an electrochemical reaction between the anode and the cathode of the two phases. During the etching process, an orange color fume was evolved. This fume may be selenium fluoride or hydride which is poisonous. Therefore, it is strongly recommended that the etching procedure must be carried out in a venting hood. The SEM photographs of the longitudinal and transverse sections of the etched eutectics are given in Figs. 3a and 3b. In Fig. 3b, it shows that the eutectic grain boundaries are made of the SnSe phase and the eutectic grains do not have the same orientation.

The use of a sealed quartz tube hinders the one-dimensional heat extraction during crystal growth. It is expected that an improved crucible design would be able to decrease the number of eutectic grains in the transverse section of an ingot. Since silica has a thermal conductivity value of 0.012 cal/cm°C and graphite has a value of 0.16 cal/cm°C sec., the use of graphite as a

Large thermal mass at the lower end of the ampoule is an appraisable approach. The X-ray spectrum of the unetched SnSe₂ phase at 29 KeV of electron beam is in agreement with those of the grown SnSe₂. Based on these comparisons, it is concluded that the SnSe phase can be preferentially etched away in one minute with a mixture solution of 1 part of HF and 1 part of HNO₃. The immersion of a wafer, cut perpendicular to the growth axis, into this solution will eventually end up with microplatelets of the SnSe₂ phase.

Confirmation of Multi-P/N-Layer Structure

Hot probe method was used to check the semiconductivity of SnSe-SnSe₂ eutectics. Although two point probes were used in this case, the contact area is much larger than the size of an individual phase (2-4 micrometer). As a result, only n-type conductivity was detected. Since the SnSe-SnSe₂ eutectic has (001) of the SnSe phase (orthogonal) parallel to (001) of the SnSe₂ phase (15) (hexagonal), both compounds have {001} as their cleavage plane. Ordinary scotch tape was used to cleave layers off the eutectic wafer with their cleaved surfaces parallel to the growth axis. Hot probe measurements on the cleaved surfaces showed the n- and p-type conductivity. The explanation for this p-n junction characteristic of the SnSe-SnSe₂ eutectic is due to the nonstoichiometric features of SnSe and SnSe₂ compounds. Thus, the cation-rich side of the SnSe₂ compound displays n-type semiconductivity and the anion-rich side of the SnSe₂ compound reveals p-type semiconductivity.

Reflectance Measurement

A resistivity measurement with four point probe yielded an average value of 0.6 ohm-cm. Since direct contact to each phase is not possible at the present time, there has been no suitable technique to measure the carrier concentration of each phase of the eutectic directly. Thus, a contactless method using infrared reflection (16) to detect the plasma edge has been tried on the eutectic. At plasma wavelength, the reflection becomes metallic and a substantial peak of reflectivity close to unity appears in the reflectance spectrum. The plasma frequency, ω_p , is given by $\omega_p^2 = 4\pi q^2 N / m^* \epsilon_0$, where q is the electron charge, N is the carrier concentration, m^* is the effective mass and ϵ_0 is the dielectric constant. The infrared reflectivity has been measured from 2.5 to 40 micron wavelength on the eutectic surface of transverse sections using a spectrophotometer (Perkin-Elmer Model 457) in conjunction with a microspecular reflectance accessory (Barnes Engineering Company, Model 126). Figure 4 shows the reflectance spectrum of a SnSe-SnSe₂ eutectics. The total reflectivity (R) can be written as $R = aR_1 + bR_2$, where R_1 and R_2 are the reflectivities of SnSe and SnSe₂, respectively, and a and b are the percentage of the SnSe and SnSe₂ surface areas, respectively. The reflectance data indicated that the carrier concentrations of both phases are not such heavily doped that the plasma edge can be detected within 40 micron of wavelength.

Current Voltage Characteristic

A current-voltage measurement of a SnSe film on a SnSe-SnSe₂ eutectic composite substrate has been made (5) and it showed a p-n junction diode characteristic. Due to a fragile nature of the SnSe-SnSe₂ eutectic, it was unsuccessful to fabricate a solar cell for electrical measurement. However, a photoresponse was observed with an instant light illuminating the SnSe film of a p-n junction device.

Before utilizing the multi-p/n-junction eutectics as solid-static-device materials, it is necessary to prepare a single p-n junction for characterization. Therefore, several large SnSe single crystals have been grown (17) by the close-tube-vapor-transport technique. These crystals were used as substrates for making single p-n junctions for electrical measurement. The current voltage characteristic of one of many single-p/n-junction devices is shown in Fig. 5 which is the fourth-quadrant portion of a solar cell. The open-circuit voltage, V_{OC} , and the shortcircuit current, I_{SC} , were determined by a curve tracer for a

given light level. The maximum power delivered to a load occurs when the product IV is a maximum. Since the V_{OC} (0.033 volts) and I_{SC} (0.5 mA) of this single-junction device are small, the maximum delivered power is also small. If a solar cell is made of thousands of these junctions, then the delivered power could be very large. Therefore, it is tentatively concluded that the multi-p/n-junction eutectic composite has a potential for electronic device applications.

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Figure 1. SnSe-SnSe₂ eutectic of 18 mm diameter

Figure 2. Wafers of SnSe-SnSe₂ eutectic

Figure 3a. SEM Picture of longitudinal Section of a SnSe-SnSe₂ eutectic (X74)

Figure 3b. SEM Picture of transverse section of a SnSe-SnSe₂ eutectic (X115)

Fig. 4 Reflectance spectrum of SnSe-SnSe₂ eutectic

Fig. 5 Current-Voltage Curves of an n-p (SnSe₂ film on SnSe substrate) Heterojunction Photovoltaic Cell in the Dark & under Illumination

